
**An Analytical Study of Stress Management Regarding Non-Teaching Staff
of Senior Colleges with Special Reference to Arts, Science, And Commerce
Colleges in Akole Tehsil**

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DOI - 10.5281/zenodo.15532767

Abstract:

If we consider the concept of stress in the environment of the non-teaching staff of colleges, it is inevitable. There are various modes of conduct to handle the stress that is supposed to be followed in the stress management of non-teaching staff. They are living away from their house, having financial struggles, academic pressure, the behavior of their senior, the issue with relationships of family members, the additional workload of non-grant division and course, low confidence, feeling scared of disciplinary action, anxiety, and uncomfortable, all the time, sleeping less, etc. Hence, it is necessary to solve these problems like proper sleep, focusing on health and nutrition, expressing feelings with family members, consulting with a doctor regarding a health issue or nerve system, proper planning of academic work, filling the vacancies of the additional post, workshop on motivation and humanity, morale support from the family, etc. The primary objective of this study is to focus on stress, and its impact on the nonteaching staff, its influence on solutions to these problems, and to promote a healthy atmosphere among the staff to survive in college with better and positive confidence.

Keywords - Stress Management, Financial Struggle, Academic Pressure, Health Issue, Positivity, Mental Health

Introduction:

Stress can lead to other, more serious mental illnesses. In India, one out of every four people is found to be suffering from stress. Sometimes we cannot concentrate properly on work. It affects work. This problem occurs due to stress in the person. Not taking proper care of stress increases the chances of developing mental illness. If these diseases are not treated, their severity increases and affects the mental health of the person badly. It has been seen that three fourth of the total patients treated for stress and depression in the country are women. In present times be it due to work or personal life. But every human being is seen living under stress. The result of this stress is the current era has become so much that people

are running for money, success, and a bright future only. Everyone just wants to be successful and rich by making money. But while running after all these, human beings are losing one big thing which is mental happiness and peace, and instead, stress is falling on them. A person is very much busy with the noise of work, successful life, that he is not aware of day and night. Apart from work, due to worldly responsibilities, and worries in life, a person gets trapped in the throes of stress. The cumulative effect of this is that entire lives are ruined. Without mental happiness, staff cannot be happy. There is no satisfaction in what one gets. Hence, we are going to focus on getting this stress and relief from it. It is called stress management.

Need and Importance of the Study:

College working life is full of new challenges, passion, excitement, fun, and also concern with problems and stress. Although college work can seem very exciting, many workers i.e. non-teaching staff feel a lot of pressure during this time. This stress can become dangerous if the pressure increases. Hence, in this study, we have to focus on this problem and fight for a new life, healthy life, and stress-less life for workers i.e. non-teaching staff. Because the nonteaching staff is the real asset of colleges.

Not taking proper care of stress increases the chances of developing mental illness. If these diseases are not treated, their severity increases and affects the mental health of the nonteaching staff badly.

Objectives of the Study:

1. To study the impact of different types of stress on nonteaching.
2. To analyze and interpret various views and opinions of nonteaching regarding stress,
3. To find out various issues related to stress and to provide appropriate suggestions.

The Hypothesis of the Study:

1. Stress creates a negative impact on nonteaching staff.
2. The relief of stress depends upon the mental ability and understanding level of nonteaching staff.

Research Methodology:

For analysis and evaluation of the topic, the researcher has used both types of data sources i.e., primary and secondary data sources. Primary data was collected from nonteaching consisting of senior colleges of arts, Science, and Commerce, colleges in Akole Tehsil. Secondary data was collected from reference articles from online mode. 300 non-teaching staff from various classes

filled out and submitted questionnaires to understand their opinion about stress and its impact. Thus, out of these 300 samples of non-teaching staff, the researcher has selected 250 males and 50 females for the study based on a simple convenient random sample method. The said non-teaching staff is selected from different colleges. In addition to this, the researcher has conducted interviews with 03 Principals and 02 Registrars of arts, science, and commerce colleges. To understand their views on the provision of stress, the researcher has used the interview method for data collection.

Findings of the Study:

1. Out of the total nonteaching, 105 (35%) respondents opined that they are suffering from the impact of stress due to living far away from their families. The Feelings of loneliness due to being away from home. Because it's their first time living away from home.
2. It is found that 90 (30%) respondents go to stress due to financial struggles. Daily inflation of necessary commodities also affected the minds of the respondents. The rising cost is a source of stress for many low-income level families.
3. When asked about academic pressure, it is found that 54(18%) sample respondents ticked towards it. Academic performance is the most common stressor in college. Negativity is occurred in the mental health of respondents due to academic pressure.
4. When asked about the behavior of their senior, it is found that 225 (75%) sample respondents opined that the said causes create stress in the minds of the respondents. Seniors always keep employees in awe. But taking them for granted hurts other important aspects of life overall.
5. It is found that 162 (54%) sample respondents opined that they have an issue with relationships. A college is an excellent place of prestige for non-

teaching staff. But, if these connections go wrong, the respondents may get significant stress and anxiety.

6. 144 (48%) sample respondents opined that they suffer from the stress of additional workload. Starting various non-grant classes and subjects increases workload and results in physical stress among the non-teaching staff.
7. A confident person believes in his abilities. Confidence is expressed by showing confidence. Many times due to a lack of self-confidence, assigned responsibilities cannot be completed on time. Fear of failure reduces self-confidence accordingly. In the study of 165(55%) the sample respondents opined they have very fewer confidence levels.
8. It is found that most of the 270 (90%) respondents are feeling scared due to negativities. It creates stress in the minds of the respondent anxious, and uncomfortable, all the time.
9. All the sample Principals thought that there is a problem for all respondents that they have very less sleep due to additional responsibilities at the time of examination. Due to this, some respondents get stressed in the workplace.
10. All the sample registrars thought that some nonteaching staff gets stressed due to family clashes, divorce, and other family issues. The said problem was faced by 15 sample respondents (10 %).
11. Human resource is the prime asset of the organization and educational institute. But people were far away from the positivity of work, and view of life.

Suggestions and Discussion:

1. There is a dire need to inculcate techniques such as avoiding excess caffeine, turning down the lights, or putting away technology at least one hour before bed. It minimizes sleep deprivation and insomnia.

2. Researchers strongly felt that respondents develop good habits like eating a balanced diet with exercising regularly. With the help of that, they get enough sleep can help manage stress. It prevents dramatic weight loss or weight gain.
3. Regular exercise activities naturally teach respondents how to increase overall health and can reduce stress. Exercise is effective in reducing fatigue, improving mental clarity, and influencing cognitive function.
4. There is a need that family members should deliberately try to involve their Karta of the family in communication. They should be enhanced on confidence building of respondents and try to away from family clashes. Because the communication gap is affected the mentality of the respondent.
5. There is a dire need to provide importance to a healthy outlet to turn to in times of stress can help the mind and clarify to move forward in a stressful situation. Some parameters like a hobby, social club, and physical exercise can be outlets for relieving stress.
6. Respondent must also be advised that there are numerous benefits of having a solid support system in the college. Personal and family, friend connections provide stress-free hormones that counter the body's fight-or-flight response.
7. Researchers strongly believe that Stress creates tension in the body through stiff and sore muscles, headaches, or lowered immune systems. Respondents must be having a spa day, taking a bubble bath, meditating, or taking themselves on a date are just some of the ideas that can practice relaxation.
8. In this study, it is found from secondary data that the youngster has shown a growing susceptibility to diseases, allergies, and mental health issues. Enhancing time management strategies

helps to stay organized and better prioritize the most important tasks.

9. Researchers strongly believe that there is a need that every college, educational institution, and administration should provide attention to the minds of the respondents with the help of regular meet with the non-teaching staff of the college in a free environment and staff-oriented activities like festivals and extra curriculum.
10. There is a need for financial support from the government and organizations, and Principals, on the financial assistance of the staff, especially in the admission fee, and other charges of the college and hostels for their family members. Irrespective of that they must provide the facility of an installment system.
11. Researchers strongly believe that there is a need that every college administration should provide adequate enhancement to the statement that non-teaching is part of human resources. They are an asset to the educational institute. It promotes mindfulness helps to drown out the background noise and increases awareness.

Conclusion:

Stress management activities are essential to developing the non-teaching physically as well as mentally. It changes the personality of individuals. Stress management boosts the discipline, team spirit, mental ability, confidence, and concentration of non-teaching staff. There is a need to provide facilities to make staff interested in a stress-free life. Considering the current college environment, there is a need for extra facilities in every college such as swimming pools and indoor and outdoor game facilities to focus on the pressure-free life of the staff. More attention must be given to those non-teaching staff that is identified as interested in entertainment and other negative activities. More physical

activities could motivate them to keep aside from negative activities. Stress management should form an integral part of the curriculum of every college and university. Colleges should be well equipped with all facilities which motivate the staff to live with free life.

Stress can lead to other, more serious mental illnesses. In India, one out of every four people is found to be suffering from stress. Sometimes we cannot concentrate properly on work. It affects work. This problem occurs due to stress in the person. Not taking proper care of stress increases the chances of developing mental illness. If these diseases are not treated, their severity increases and affects the mental health of the person badly. A person is very much busy with the noise of work, successful life, career-oriented life that he is not aware of day and night. Apart from work, study due to worldly responsibilities, and worries in life, a person gets trapped in the throes of stress. The cumulative effect of this is that entire lives are ruined. Without mental happiness, staff cannot be happy. There is no satisfaction in what one gets. Hence, we are going to focus on getting this stress and relief from it. It is called stress management.

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